

Shedding Light on the Dark: Distrust as a Distinct Concept in Stakeholder Relationships

Antoinette Weibel, Tiziana Gaito, Simon Schafheitle, Sybille Sachs

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Abstract

In response to calls for a more comprehensive understanding of stakeholder relationships, this study complements the well-established “bright side,” where trust enables value creation through shared interests and values, with the “dark side,” where conflicts and harmful behavior lead to negative outcomes in relationships between focal organizations and their stakeholders. To refine the boundary conditions of the dark side, we conceptualize distrust in stakeholder relationships and introduce stakeholder distrust, defined as the collective unwillingness of a focal organization to accept vulnerability, as a relational construct distinct from both stakeholder trust and suspicion. We develop a causal model of stakeholder distrust and outline several propositions regarding its antecedents and consequences. These distinctions, together with the causal model, (i) advance stakeholder examination, (ii) inform stakeholder engagement, and (iii) refine our understanding of the relational dynamics underlying stakeholder relationships. Collectively, they support a more nuanced examination of stakeholder relationships, facilitate the identification of early warning signals in ongoing interactions, and suggest how distrust can be addressed through stakeholder engagement practices, which include methods, tools, and routines that structure interactions with stakeholders. Accordingly, we advance theoretical understanding of stakeholder distrust while offering practical approaches to prevent and resolve conflicts and harmful behavior.

Keywords: Dark side, Distrust, Stakeholder engagement, Stakeholder theory, Suspicion, Interorganisational

Note on Availability

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